

SOCIALIZATION OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Eshchanova Gulnara Narimanovna

TDPU in the name of Nizomi "Pedagogy of preschool education and associate professor of the psychology department, Ph.D

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7542060>

Abstract. *The article highlights the positive aspects of sociological research carried out in order to increase and improve the quality of preschool education services, while opinions and comments about the preschool education system and its sociology are based on the views and researches of well-known sociologists.*

Keywords: *sociological approach, values, system, preschool education, early childhood, family, pedagogical process.*

Education is important in any society. Education prepares children for social life and ensures that they are active in various fields. Taking this into account, attention is being paid to the quality of education in today's age of technology and information. In the developed countries of the world, social concepts of various fields of education are being developed. This has a positive effect on improving the intelligence of the country's population.

The educational reforms being carried out in our country envisage improvement of the field at the level of modern requirements and achieving quality education of the young generation. A clear example of this is the reforms implemented for the development of our children as mature individuals in all aspects, and the scientific researches carried out in the field. We will be able to know about the reforms in the field of education and how they have worked and are working through the sociology of education. At this point, it is permissible to answer the question of what is the sociology of education and what is analyzed in it.

French sociologist E. Durkheim and German sociologist M. Weber are recognized as the founders of sociology of education.[1] In their research, they studied the social tasks of education, its place in society: economic and political processes.

In particular, in Weber's theory of social action, he distinguishes four types: goal-oriented, value-oriented, traditional and affective. Weber's principles can be applied to the activities of preschool education organizations. Because Weber puts the individual above everything else and called the cultural-spiritual (belonging to us) values as the basis for society.[2] The American sociologist T. Parsons, who was thoroughly acquainted with the works of the above-mentioned scientists, proposed to study education as a socialization institution, and educational institutions as a social system.

When we talk about the reforms in the system of preschool education in our country and the nature of the purpose of this system, we are convinced of the rightness of the opinions presented in Parsons' article "Sociological approach to the theory of organization" [3]. Parsons defines an organization as a social system aimed at achieving specific goals, which in turn helps to achieve the goals of a wider social system. In fact, the goals set for preschool education organizations today are clear: to educate children for socialization, to develop the concept of "I" in children, and to prepare them for school education. According to the sociological model created by Parsons, in order to implement this social activity, the preschool educational organization should carry out systematic activities to demonstrate its place in society. Based on Parson's model,

we will try to sociologically analyze the activities of preschool educational organizations. In this case, the pedagogical process in the preschool education organization should be properly and systematically organized, creating suitable conditions for the adaptation of young children to the preschool education organization; Ensuring the socialization of young children, clear "setting goals and determining the ways to achieve them (goal achievement)"; organization of pedagogical processes in accordance with the requirements of the time and the areas of development and age characteristics of the child, educational programs and educational programs necessary for the socialization of the child and the achievement of pedagogical goals. organization of game activities; In order to implement the requirements of the "State Standard of Preschool Education and Education" introduced into the system, it is possible to achieve the socialization of preschool children and improve self-development skills in children by collecting, systematizing and transferring normative samples. To fulfill these requirements, developing positive competition in the field, that is, providing education to children in state preschool educational organizations, private, family, and preschool education organizations operating on the basis of public and private partnerships: their social adaptation; orientation of education to the child's personality; integration of education and upbringing; attention to intellectual and aesthetic, physical education is important. this will be a reliable factor for self-development. Our analysis shows that. The sociological model developed by Parsons considers all organizations, including preschool education organizations, as a social system aimed at achieving specific goals, which in turn helps to achieve the goals of the social system at the next stages of education. It ensures the unity of society and education, that is, it shows that the development of society depends on the development of education.

T. Parsons, based on the functional model he created, proposes to analyze the social organization using four main categories:

- flexible mechanisms aimed at resource mobilization (adaptation);
- operational code, mechanisms determining the process of achieving organizational goals (goal achievement);
- integration mechanisms (integration);
- a system of values that defines and legitimizes the goals of the organization (repeat the model).[4]

It seems that adaptive mechanisms solve the problem of resource mobilization and represent the main aspect of the relationship between the organization and its external environment. Now, if we consider this principle as an example of a preschool education organization, it will be necessary to organize the pedagogical process and the effective activity of pedagogues-educators, who are considered the main driving force in ensuring social adaptation of children to preschool education organizations. We touched on this in detail in our previous article "Analysis of the process of social adaptation of a preschool child". "Revealed the important features of the pedagogical process in preschool education organizations: the main feature of this period is the child's mastering of the rules of living together with people from one environment (family environment) to another (pre-school educational organization), the main direction in the child's development, i.e. the maturation of self-development skills and competencies will go to find out". [5]

The second category of sociological analysis of T. Parsons is the operational code, the mechanisms that determine the process of achieving the organization's goals (achieving the goal).

Taking this into account, it is necessary to use modern methods and methods of instilling love for books in children from an early age, developing creative abilities, and providing education in the spirit of national and universal human values.

As we mentioned above, one of the most important tasks of preschool education is to prepare children for school education by developing and forming their initial knowledge and skills about the socio-cultural norms and customs of the family, society and the state in accordance with the state standard. While researching the socialization of preschool children, we witness that their relationships with family members and adults are also important in their formation. Appropriate use of thematic conversations, problem situations, games, theater, and social folk tales in teaching preschool children social and cultural values is important in achieving the goal. It is clear that the most convenient and effective period for perfecting social and spiritual values and mental-intellectual development in a person is the pre-school period. [6] Now it is necessary to dwell on the set of mechanisms necessary to achieve the intended goal in this period. First of all, it is necessary to create conditions for pedagogues-educators working in preschool education organizations to "develop self and creative potential, improve creative, communicative abilities and active life positions, implement humanitarian principles and person-oriented education. Ensuring positive competitiveness between different types of pre-school education organizations, creating alternative educational programs to the "First Step" and "Ilm Yoli" educational programs.

Parsons' third category is directly related to the management system, which refers to the systematic management based on fair values in the preschool education organization. For this purpose, it is appropriate to work based on universal values, following the rules regulating economic and social transactions, because the preschool educational organization is a moral-intellectual field, like all organizations of the spiritual and educational level of society. Political decisions define the organization as an entity that realizes its goals in the external environment. Such a definition refers to the organization's commitment to the wider community. An organization has a distribution of personnel (authority and responsibility) and material and financial resources (opportunities and rewards).[7]

In our opinion, sociological research is the basis for developing activities of preschool educational organizations and determining its strategy and tactics in modern sociology of education. Sociological research allows collecting, processing, summarizing, analyzing and predicting the data necessary to solve the existing problems in the preschool education system. Sociological research serves as a summary of the quality and efficiency of the pedagogical process in preschool education organizations s. [8].

Sociology of education is a branch of sociology that studies the laws of functioning of education as a social institution (tasks in society, relations with other institutions, social policy in the field of education, value orientations of specialists, educational systems and structures, relations), education of various socio-demographic groups, management of educational institutions and staffing issues, etc.), preschool education organizations also have a number of sociological problems, and in this article we touched on some of its aspects.

With the help of sociological research conducted in order to improve the quality of pre-school education services, harmony is being achieved in the development of society and education. Preschool education ensures healthy, all-round development of the child, increases his enthusiasm for studying, prepares him to study with enthusiasm at the next stages of education.. Preschool education ensures the child's healthy, all-round development, increases his motivation

to study, and prepares him to learn with enthusiasm in the next stages of education. In order to increase and improve the quality of pre-school education, the following should be implemented: - improvement of the professional competence of future pedagogues-educators in his in the field of pedagogy, taking into account the need for qualified educators and specialists; Improvement of qualification and retraining of pedagogues-educators working in preschool education organizations; improvement and implementation of modern teaching methods, technical tools, methods of creating games of educational significance; Providing preschool education organizations with modern information and communication technologies and establishing effective and appropriate use of these services; To create and put into practice the mechanism of sociological research for the purpose of comprehensive analysis of preschool education organization activity.

REFERENCES

1. Эмиле Дюркеим – Википедия <https://uz.википедия.орг> > вики, Вебер, Макс – Википедия <https://ru.википедия.орг> > вики > Вебер,_Макс
2. Вишневецкий С. Ю. М. Вебер и становление социологической категории «Призвание» // Дискуссия. 2012. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/m-veber-i-stanovlenie-sotsiologicheskoy-kategorii-prizvanie> (дата обращения: 14.01.2023).
3. Парсонс Т. Система современных обществ. - М.: Аспект пресс, 1997. - С. 16-24..
4. Парсонс Т. А Сосоиологисал аппроасҳ то тхе тхеорй оф организатионс // Административе ссиенсе куартерлий - Жуне. - 1956.
5. Narimanovna E. G., Yusufovna G. V. SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT OF THE PRESCHOOL CHILD PROCESS ANALYSIS //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education. – 2022. – Т. 14. – №. 7.
6. Шаропова Н. Р. “Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар” илмий электрон журнали. № 4, июль-август, 2018 йил “Мақтабгача таълимда маркетинг тадқиқотларини амалга оширишнинг хориж тажрибаси”
7. Мацкевич Ирина Владимировна Организация и социальная структура (взгляд Т. Парсонса) // Вестник БГУ. 2015. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organizatsiya-i-sotsialnaya-struktura-vzglyad-t-parsonsa> (дата обращения:
8. Author description
9. Eshchanova, G. (2022). Maktabgacha ta’lim tizimidagi islohotlar sotsializatsiyasi. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 561-564.